

Integrated germplasm improvement

IET9783 : a salt-tolerant rice for coastal saline soil

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Coastal saline soil occurs in a narrow strip along the Bay of Bengal, 375 km long and 2.25 km wide and covering 2.54 million ha. Rice is the main crop of wet season (WS), fields are fallow in dry season (DS). In a year of poor monsoon, the crop fails.

The Regional Research Station, Motto, is situated on the coast 10 km away from the Bay of Bengal. Soil is

fine clayey, mixed, hyperthermic family, Vertic Halaquept; pH of the experimental site was 7.2 in WS and 8.0 in DS. EC values were 1.2-6.8 dS/m during Jul-Nov and 2.7-13.5 dS/m during Dec-Mar.

In 1987-88 DS, we evaluated 28 cultivars from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad, 2 resistant checks, and local checks SR26-B in WS and CSR4 (Mohan). The experiments were in a randomized block design with three replications.

Three 35-old seedlings/variety were transplanted on 25 Jul 1987 and 9 Jan 1988 at 20- × 15-cm spacing in 4-m² plots. Fertilizer was 60-26 kg NP/ ha.

The WS crop was rainfed; the DS crop was irrigated with poor quality lift irrigation water.

IET10676 yielded highest (4.0 t/ha) in WS (see table). Soil salinity delayed crop maturity in DS 1149 d, and yields did not differ significantly. □

Performance of rice varieties and cultivars in coastal saline soil at Motto, Balasore, India, 1987-88 WS and DS.

Cultivar	Parentage	Duration (d)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
		ws	DS	ws	DS
IET10344	SAR41/Jaya	111	123	2.1	1.0
IET10345	SAR43/IR8	110	130	2.0	0.6
IET10346	IR1702-74-3/IR2061464-2	129	156	1.7	0.8
IET10348	CSR1/Basmati370//CSR5	134	154	2.2	1.1
IET10349	M40-431-24-114/Jaya	110	143	1.8	1.3
CSR1 Mutant	CSR1	111	134	1.3	1.1
IET10354	—	113	133	2.3	1.4
IET10357	Rasi/IET6238	114	156	1.3	0.7
IET10358	IET6238/IR36	116	150	1.2	0.3
IETT9783	—	115	155	1.6	2.0
IET10672	CO 22 / Vaigai	105	153	1.3	0.7
IET9784	—	115	126	1.1	0.4
IET10675	—	115	137	3.0	1.2
IET10683	TNI/CO 29	102	141	3.1	0.4
IET10676	—	127	166	4.0	0.7
IET10684	IR13240-108-2-2-3/ IR9129-209-2-2-2-1	120	137	2.0	1.1
IET10685	T22/Mahsuri	117	166	2.2	0.5
IET10689	TNI/CSR5	122	167	2.9	0.5
CSR 1 Mutant	CSR1	120	137	2.6	0.7
IET10692	—	106	139	2.4	0.9
ET10693	M40-431-24-114/ Basmati 370	122	154	2.9	0.8
IET10694	M40-431-24-114/Jaya	116	141	3.2	1.4
IET10696	IR36/MR340	115	139	2.9	1.1
IET10697	IET6238/MR340	106	141	2.8	1.0
IET10698	IET6238/Mk340	125	139	2.3	1.4
IET10699	IET6238/MR342	113	138	3.1	1.7
Pokkali (resistant check)	—	125	136	1.9	0.8
Vikas (resistant check)	—	125	141	0.8	0.8
SR26-B (local check)	—	155	—	2.7	—
Damodar (local check)	—	—	140	—	0.8
Mohan (local check)	—	—	152	—	1.6
LSD (0.05)		2.3	10.9	0.5	n.s.

Performance of upland and rainfed lowland rice varieties in farmers' fields in Mali

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Rice variety trials in farmers' fields of the Operation Haute Vallée (OHV) were carried out in collaboration with the Multilocational Unit of the Institute of Rural Economy and USAID farming systems research (FSR/ E) project.

Upland soils were sandy loam, lowland soils were hydromorphic with some standing water during some periods of the cropping season. Ammonium phosphate and urea were applied at 100 kg/ha in lowland and 50 kg/ha in upland. Urea was applied at planting and at panicle initiation. Two farmers each for upland and lowland conditions conducted trials, with four replications.

In upland conditions, the introduced varieties had almost three times the yield of the local check (see table). In lowland

Grain yield and approximate duration of selected rice varieties in farmers' fields testing in the Operation Haute Vallée project, Mali, 1987-88 cropping season.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)
<i>Upland conditions</i>		
Linke ^a	0.6	100
IRAT144	1.8	110
Dourado	1.6	103
<i>Lowland conditions</i>		
BG90-2	2.5	124
IET2911	2.5	127
BKNLR75001	2.2	129

^a Local check; farmers in lowland conditions did not have a local variety.